

THE ROLE OF STANDARD CYTOGENETIC TESTING IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE MYELOID LEUKEMIA.

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The relevance of the problem. Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a clonal malignant disease characterized by ineffective hematopoiesis. Most patients with AML have various cytogenetic and molecular genetic lesions that are combined with certain biological and clinical features of the disease. Approximately 50–60% of patients *de novo* and 80–95% of patients with secondary AML have chromosomal changes. It should be noted that structural cytogenetic aberrations are the most common markers and occur in approximately 40% of AML cases *de novo*. A fairly large group of patients with a normal karyotype (NC-AML), formally classified as intermediate risk, is extremely heterogeneous in terms of prognosis of the disease course. The current prognostic classifications of AML today include only some mutations characterized by a known prognostic value, in particular $t(8; 21)$, NPM1 and BRAF.

Classical karyotype analysis can detect chromosomal changes in approximately half of patients with AML. Many chromosomal aberrations are independent prognostic factors and are included in the current classification of AML published by the World Health Organization (WHO).

Although some mutations are already included in the current WHO classification and recommendations of European experts, a more detailed study of the molecular architecture of leukemia is necessary.

The aim of the study was to study the frequency of driver somatic mutations in patients with AML depending on chromosomal changes.

Material and methods of research. Material for molecular_ The genetic study was performed on the peripheral blood of 145 patients with AML who were in hospital treatment at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Clinical and laboratory studies were performed at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Hematology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The results obtained and their discussion.

karyotyping of cells was performed in 83 patients out of 145 examined patients . In accordance with the objectives of the study, we performed a karyotype analysis using the standard cytogenetic study (SGS) method in patients with AML.

During standard cytogenetic testing, karyotype changes were detected in 32 out of 83 patients (38.6%), while chromosomal aberrations were not detected in 51 patients (61.4%) (karyotype 46XX or 46XY).

In male patients, chromosomal abnormalities were found in 19 of 39 (48.7%) patients, and no karyotype abnormalities were detected in 20 patients (51.3%). In the group of female patients, chromosomal aberrations were detected in 13 of 44 (29.5%) patients, and no karyotype changes were detected in 31 patients (70.5%). Chromosomal aberrations were registered more frequently among males compared to females. In young patients, karyotype abnormalities were detected in 33.3% of cases (22 of 66), normal karyotype was detected in 66.7% (44 of 66) patients, respectively. In elderly patients, chromosomal abnormalities were registered in 10 of 17 patients (58.8%), normal karyotype was detected in 7 of 17 patients (41.2%).

Thus, chromosomal aberrations were registered most frequently among men and in elderly patients.

During the study of the t (8 ; 21) mutation were detected in 9.7% (14 of 145) patients, while mutation of this gene was not detected in 90.3% of cases, respectively. In 5 of 14 (35.7%) patients, only single mutations were detected. In 9 of 14 (64.3%) patients, mutations were combined. Mutations of this genetic marker were statistically insignificantly more often detected in patients with an altered karyotype - in 6 (18.8%) of 32 examined patients in relation to patients without them ($\chi^2 = 0.1$; OR = 1.2; p = 0.7; 95% CI : 0.39 -3.98). In the group of patients with a favorable karyotype, t (8 ; 21) mutations were detected in only 15.7% of patients

Mutations in the inv (16;9) gene were detected in 4 (2.8%) of 145 patients with AML. This mutation was not registered in 141 (97.2%) of 145. In all cases, the mutation of the above-mentioned gene was combined.

When studying patients depending on the karyotype, it was found that the highest incidence of mutations in the inv (16, 9) gene was detected in the group of patients with a normal karyotype – in 3 (5.9%) of 51 patients. In the group of patients with chromosomal aberrations, the incidence of mutation of the studied gene was found in 1 of 32 patients (3.1%). Despite this, the differences in the

incidence of mutation of the inv (16, 9) gene in patients with a normal karyotype and with an altered karyotype were statistically insignificant ($\chi^2 = 0.3$; OR = 0.5; $p = 0.6$; 95% CI : 0.05 – 5).

In the study, mutations in the NPM 1 gene were detected in 17.2% of patients, and in 82.8% of cases this mutation was not registered.

the NPM 1 gene were detected in 16 of 25 patients. Combined mutations were registered in the remaining 9 of 25 patients.

The study demonstrated a significantly higher frequency of distribution of the NPM 1 mutation in patients with a normal karyotype compared to patients with chromosomal abnormalities (35.3% versus 9.4% with $\chi^2 = 7.0$; OR = 0.2; $p = 0.01$; 95% CI : 0.06 – 0.65).

Conclusion. Thus, during the standard cytogenetic study, karyotype changes were detected in 38.6% of patients, while in 61.4% of cases, chromosomal aberrations were not detected. Chromosomal aberrations were registered most often among men and in elderly patients. In patients with a normal karyotype, insertions in the genes NPM 1, inv (16;9) are more often detected, while mutations in the genes t (8;21) were more common in patients with an altered karyotype.

